

THE INSTRUCTIONAL CHALLENGES OF OUT-OF-FIELD TEACHING AND ITS IMPACT ON TEACHERS' COMPETENCE AND MOTIVATION

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ABSTRACT

Out-of-field teaching, a growing phenomenon in many education systems, occurs when teachers are assigned to teach subjects outside their area of expertise due to teacher shortages. This study investigates the instructional challenges faced by teachers in such situations and explores their impact on their professional competence and motivation. Conducted at the Isabela School of Arts and Trades (ISAT) in the Philippines, the research employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews. The study identifies several challenges, including content and pedagogy, classroom management, addressing learner diversity, and curriculum adaptation. Teachers expressed concerns about the increased workload, reduced confidence, and challenges in creating effective lesson plans. Despite these difficulties, the research highlights teachers' resilience, as many employ coping strategies such as seeking professional development, collaborating with colleagues, and using technology to enhance their teaching. The findings suggest that while out-of-field teaching negatively impacts teachers' instructional competence, it also motivates them to seek personal and professional growth. These challenges underscore the need for targeted support, training, and mentoring programs to improve teachers' capabilities and confidence in handling out-of-field subjects, ultimately ensuring the delivery of quality education.

Keywords: *Out-of-field teaching, instructional challenges, teacher competence, teacher motivation, professional development.*

INTRODUCTION

The pursuit of high-quality education hinges on effective teaching, ideally delivered by educators specializing in the subjects they teach. Teachers teaching their specialized subjects possess in-depth knowledge, enabling them to explain concepts clearly, address complex questions effectively, and provide nuanced perspectives. This deep understanding fosters a more engaging and enriching learning experience. However, the reality often falls short. Many educational systems, including the Philippines, face challenges such as teacher shortages. This necessitates teachers to play multifaceted roles, requiring not only subject matter expertise but also pedagogical skill and the ability to foster a positive learning environment. While ideal teaching practices emphasize alignment between a teacher's specialization and the subjects they teach, the reality in many educational systems, including the Philippines, is often different.

Teacher shortages, exacerbated by factors such as the implementation of the K-12 program, frequently lead school leaders to make difficult decisions and assign teachers to teach subjects outside their area of expertise or specialization. This phenomenon is not unique to the Philippines; it is a global concern affecting many countries. In Australia, for example, a significant percentage of teachers with 7-10 years of experience teach outside their specialization according to Weldon (2016). In fact, the Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM 2) (2024) report revealed that sixty two percent (62%) or more than half of the Filipino secondary teachers handle subjects they are not major in. In the field of education, there are instances where teachers are assigned to teach subjects outside their specialization because of lack of qualified teachers to handle the subject. The implementation of the K-12 program adds the worsening teacher deficit in the country which influences the decision of school management to assign teachers to teach subject not of their expertise which poses negative effects on teachers' psychological well-being which can hinder the students learning.

This research aims to explore not only the difficulties teachers face when teaching outside their area of expertise but also the strategies they employ to maintain their teaching effectiveness despite these challenges.

Teaching within one's area of expertise is considered an essential factor in ensuring high-quality education. Research suggests that teachers with deep subject knowledge can deliver lessons more effectively and foster better student learning outcome (Ríordáin et al., 2019) . However, due to teacher shortages and administrative decisions, many educators are assigned to teach subjects beyond their specialization. This phenomenon, known as out-of-field teaching, presents significant challenges for teachers, including increased workload, decreased confidence, and job dissatisfaction (Huston, 2019).

Despite these challenges, some researchers argue that teaching outside one's expertise can also serve as a learning opportunity, allowing teachers to expand their knowledge and pedagogical skills (Hobbs, 2013). However, the impact of this experience on teachers' sense of competence and motivation remains an important area of study.

While existing literature has explored the effects of out-of-field teaching on instructional quality and student learning, less attention has been given to its impact on teachers' well-being and professional identity, particularly at the tertiary level (Hobbs & Törner, 2019).

The findings of this study can contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges and impacts of teaching subjects outside one's area of expertise on teachers' professional growth, competence, and motivation. This study may provide valuable insights for school administrators in developing better support systems and professional development programs for teachers assigned to unfamiliar subjects. By understanding these experiences, schools can implement more effective policies to help teachers maintain their competence and motivation, ultimately ensuring quality education for students.

The writer has personally experienced teaching subjects that she was not entirely familiar with. To effectively teach these subjects, extra time is needed for studying new content and watching educational videos about the lesson. New teaching approaches are implemented to ensure that students could understand the lesson effectively. Despite these efforts, the researcher has some doubts whether her knowledge is sufficient to meet students' learning needs. These challenges led the writer to reflect on how other teachers in similar situations cope with out-of-field teaching. The experience of teaching outside one's field is seen to have an impact on teachers' confidence and motivation. It also prompts them to develop and use various strategies to adapt to the challenges they face. Inspired by these insights, the researcher decided to conduct this study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to: examine the challenges encountered by teachers assigned to teach out-of-field subjects and its impact on their sense of competence and motivation. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of:
 - a. Highest Educational Attainment
 - b. Major/Field of specialization
 - c. Subject currently taught
 - d. Number of years of out-of-field teaching
 - e. Number of trainings related to the subject taught attended in the last 3 years
2. What are the instructional challenges encountered by the teachers in line with out-of-field teaching in terms of:
 - a. Content and pedagogy
 - b. Learning environment
 - c. Diversity of learners
 - d. Curriculum and planning
 - e. Assessment and reporting
3. Is there a significant difference on the instructional challenges encountered according to profile?
4. What coping strategies do teachers use when teaching out-of-field subjects?
5. Is there a significant difference on the coping strategies and profile?

6. What is the impact of out-of-field teaching on their instructional competence and motivation?
7. Is there a significant relationship between coping strategies and impact of out-of-field teaching?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive research, integrating both quantitative and qualitative research methods to provide a comprehensive examination of the challenges and impacts of teaching out-of-field subjects on teachers' sense of competence and motivation. The quantitative component involved a survey questionnaire designed to collect numerical data on teachers' self-reported sense of competence, motivation, and challenges faced while teaching out-of-field subjects. Meanwhile, the qualitative component included in-depth interviews with selected teachers to gain deeper insights into their personal experiences, coping strategies, and perceptions about how teaching out-of-field subjects affected their professional growth and motivation.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at the Isabela School of Arts and Trades (ISAT)-Main, a public secondary and vocational institution located in Calamagui 2nd, City of Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines. It was established in 1908 by American Thomasite teachers as the Isabela Provincial Shop, initially offering woodworking courses for boys. Over the years, it evolved into the Isabela Trade School, later renamed the Isabela Regional School of Arts and Trades (IRSAT), and finally Isabela School of Arts and Trades (ISAT). The school gradually expanded its programs to include female students and various technical courses such as Automotive, Electronics, Building Construction, Cosmetology, and Furniture and Cabinet-Making.

Throughout its history, ISAT underwent multiple infrastructure improvements, including new buildings for academic and shop subjects, an athletic oval, gymnasium, and administrative offices. It also established satellite schools in San Antonio and Rang-Ayan, Ilagan to serve nearby communities. The school offered post-secondary and non-degree courses, and temporarily came under TESDA supervision before returning to DepEd administration.

ISAT operates two campuses: the main campus in Calamagui 2nd and an annex in Cabannungan 2nd. For School Year 2025–2026, the ISAT-main campus in Calamagui 2nd serves a total of 2,786 students, with 1,670 in Junior High School (JHS) and 1,116 in Senior High School (SHS), and a teaching staff of 136 teachers.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of this study were the 27 teachers who are assigned to teach subject outside of their field of expertise at Isabela School of Arts and Trades (ISAT)-Main. The study made use of purposive sampling.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Respondents	Field of specialization	Subjects taught
Teacher A	Social Studies	Science, Social Studies
Teacher B	Social Studies	Science, Social Studies
Teacher C	Technical-Vocational Education	Technical-Vocational Education, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
Teacher D	Technical-Vocational Education	Technical-Vocational Education, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
Teacher E	Technical-Vocational Education	Technical-Vocational Education, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
Teacher F	Technical-Vocational Education	Technical-Vocational Education, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
Teacher G	Technical-Vocational Education	Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
Teacher H	Technical-Vocational Education	Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
Teacher I	Technical-Vocational Education	Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
Teacher J	Technical-Vocational Education	Filipino, Technical-Vocational Education
Teacher K	Technical-Vocational Education	Filipino, Technical-Vocational Education, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
Teacher L	Technical-Vocational Education	Science
Teacher M	Technical-Vocational Education	Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (Mapeh)

Teacher N	Technical-Vocational Education	Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (Mapeh)
Teacher O	Business Technology	Computer System Servicing, Internet Computing Fundamentals
Teacher P	Electronics Technology	Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, Internet Computing Fundamentals, Automotive
Teacher Q	Mathematics	Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
Teacher R	Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao	Filipino, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
Teacher S	Technical Drawing/Drafting	Technical-Vocational Education, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, Technical Drawing/Drafting
Teacher T	English	English, Technical-Vocational Education, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao
Teacher U	Information and Communication Technology	Technical-Vocational Education, Computer System Servicing, Media and Information Literacy
Teacher V	Information and Communication Technology	Technical-Vocational Education, Media and Information Literacy, Entrepreneurship
Teacher W	English	English, Social Studies
Teacher X	Technical-Vocational Education	Media and Information Literacy, Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics, Refrigeration and Air Conditioning
Teacher Y	Technical Vocational Livelihood- (Electrical Installation and Maintenance	Mathematics
Teacher Z	Social Studies	Social Studies, Construction Operation
Teacher AA	Technical-Vocational Education ((Beauty Care)	Media and Information Literacy, Arts, Aesthetic Services
TOTAL	27	

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the study was conducted, the researcher first sent a formal letter to the Schools Division Superintendent requesting permission to conduct the study. After approval from the SDS was given, a request letter was sent to the School Head of Isabela School of Arts and Trades (ISAT)-Main to seek permission to administer the survey questionnaire in the school. After permission was granted, the researcher identified the teachers assigned to teach subjects outside their field of specialization. Consent forms were distributed to the selected respondents, ensuring their voluntary participation in the study. The survey instrument was validated and finalized before these were distributed to the respondents. Interviews were conducted with selected participants.

After the completion of the questionnaires by the respondents, these were retrieved and interview results were transcribed. Gathered data were organized, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To ensure accurate, valid, and reliable analysis of the gathered data, the following statistical tools were used:

Frequency and Percentage. This was used to analyze the profile of the respondents in terms of Highest Educational Attainment, Major/Field of specialization, Length of Service and Number of trainings related to the subject taught attended in the last 3 years.

Weighted Mean. This was used to determine the level of instructional challenges encountered by teachers teaching out-of-field, the coping strategies teachers used when teaching out-of-field subjects and the impact of out-of-field teaching on their competence and motivation.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), F-Test. This was used to determine the significant difference in the instructional challenges encountered by teachers and the coping strategies applied when grouped according to profile.

Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation, r-test. This was used to determine significant relationship between coping strategies and impact of out-of-field teaching.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of:

a. Highest Educational Attainment

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According tot their Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's Degree Graduate	11	40.7
Master's Degree	13	48.1
Doctorate	2	7.4
With MA Units	1	3.7
Total	27	100.0

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according tot their highest educational attainment. Most or 48.1 % of the respondents are master's degree holders, followed by bachelor's degree holders with 40.7%. A few or 7.4 % hold a doctorate and 3.7 % possess other qualifications The data shows that while many teachers have pursued postgraduate studies, a significant portion still teach with only an undergraduate degree. This supports the findings of Darling-Hammond (2000), who emphasized that teachers' educational qualifications are critical factors influencing instructional quality and professional readiness.

b. Major/Field of Specialization and Subject Currently Taught

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Major/Field of Specialization and Subject Currently Taught

Field of Specialization	Subject Taught on Major Field	Subjects Taught Out-of-Field	Frequency	Percentage
English	English	Social Studies, Technical-Vocational Education, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao	2	7.4
Mathematics		Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao	1	3.7
Social Studies	Social Studies	Science, Construction Operation	3	11.1
Technical-Vocational Education	Technical-Vocational Education	Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, Filipino, Science, Music, Arts, Physical Education, and		

		Health (MAPEH), Media and Information Literacy, Arts, Aesthetic Services, Understanding Culture, Society, and Politics, Refrigeration and Air Conditioning	14	51.9
Business Technology		Computer System Servicing, Internet Computing Fundamentals	1	3.7
Electronics Technology		Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao, Internet Computing Fundamentals, Automotive	1	3.7
Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao	Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao	Filipino	1	3.7
Technical Drawing/Drafting	Technical Drawing/Drafting	Technical-Vocational Education, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao	1	3.7
Information and Communication Technology		Technical-Vocational Education, Computer System Servicing, Media and Information Literacy, Entrepreneurship	2	7.4
Technical Vocational Livelihood- (Electrical Installation and Maintenance)		Mathematics	1	3.7
	Total		27	100.0

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to their major or field of specialization and the subjects they currently teach. The majority or 51.9% of respondents have specialization in Technical-Vocational Education (T.V.E.), while fewer teachers are trained in core academic subjects such as English (7.4%), Mathematics (3.7%), and Social Studies (11.1%). One or two have other specializations like Business Technology, Electronics Technology, Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (E.S.P.), Technical Drawing, ICT, and TVL-Electrical.

Regarding the subjects currently taught, most teachers are assigned out-of-field subjects. Those with specialization in TVE teach Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao or Filipino instead of their major. Similarly, teachers from other fields such as English, Social Studies, and Mathematics are assigned out-of-field subjects. Only a few teachers teach subjects aligned with their major, such as English teachers teaching English or Social Studies teachers teaching Social Studies. This distribution shows that out-of-field teaching is common in the school, particularly among TVE and technical-specialized teachers. It

reflects staffing assignments and the need to cover all subject areas. Such assignments may lead to instructional challenges, particularly related to content knowledge and pedagogical readiness.

This supports the findings of Augusto (2020), who noted that Philippine teachers teaching out-of-field subjects face instructional challenges due to gaps in content knowledge and pedagogical preparation. It is also supported by Hobbs and Porsch (2021), who emphasized that teachers assigned out-of-field may struggle with effective instruction and require professional support to maintain instructional quality.

c. Number of years of out-of-field teaching

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to the Number of years of out-of-field Teaching

Number of years of out-of-field teaching	Frequency	Percentage
1-2	4	14.8
3-4	2	7.4
5-6	10	37.0
7 or more	11	40.7
Total	27	100.0

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents' number of years teaching out-of-field subjects. A great majority or 77.7 % of the respondents have more than five years teaching subjects outside of their specialization. Further analysis of the data shows that all of the 27 teacher respondents teach subjects outside of their major field. Long-term engagement in out-of-field teaching is common among respondents, providing opportunities for teachers to develop effective coping strategies, adaptability, and professional growth. According to Augusto (2020), Philippine teachers develop adaptive strategies and professional growth through sustained out-of-field teaching.

d. Number of trainings related to the subject taught attended in the last 3 years

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to the Number of Trainings Attended Related to the Subjects Taught For the Last Three Years

Number of trainings related to the subject taught attended in the last 3 years	Frequency	Percentage
None (0)	9	33.3
1-2	9	33.3
3-4	7	25.9
5-6	1	3.7

7 or more	1	3.7
Total	27	100.0

Table 5 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to the number of trainings attended in the last three years in relation to the subjects taught in. The table shows that more than one-third of the respondents have no training at all in the subjects they teach. This is because some training programs that require specific number of teachers to attend. or require participation from certain individuals. The table also reveals that 89.2 % have attended 2 to 4 trainings in the last three years. Nevertheless, all Grade 7–8 teachers, have undergone MATATAG training. These trainings provide foundational knowledge and opportunities to enhance teaching practices, especially for teachers handling out-of-field subjects. Du Plessis et al. (2014) in her study found that targeted professional development and institutional support help teachers handle out-of-field subjects effectively.

2. What are the instructional challenges encountered by the teachers in line with out-of-field teaching in terms of:

a. Content and Pedagogy

Table 6
The Instructional Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Out-of-Field Teaching in Terms of Content and Pedagogy

Content and Pedagogy	Mean	Description
1. I find it challenging to effectively apply knowledge of content within and across teaching areas.	2.85	Agree
2. I struggle to apply research-based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning to enhance professional practice.	2.59	Agree
3. I find it difficult to integrate ICT effectively into my lessons due to my limited understanding of the subject's content and relevant digital resources.	1.93	Disagree
4. I have difficulty designing and implementing effective strategies for promoting literacy and numeracy within this subject.	2.37	Disagree
5. I find it challenging to apply a range of teaching strategies that foster critical and creative thinking skills as well as higher-order thinking skills.	2.63	Agree
Mean	2.47	Disagree

Table 6 shows the instructional challenges faced by teachers engaged in out-of-field teaching in terms of content and pedagogy. The teachers agree that they are challenged by application of content knowledge across teaching areas, application of research-based teaching principles, and the use of teaching strategies that develop critical, creative, and higher-order thinking skills. On the other hand, they disagree that integrating ICT into lessons, and promoting literacy and numeracy are challenging.

The overall mean of 2.47 implies that teachers generally find challenges on content and pedagogy to be low. The results suggest that teachers involved in out-of-field teaching are generally able to handle instructional tasks related to content and pedagogy. Still, challenges remain in areas that require strong content knowledge and advanced teaching strategies, such as applying content knowledge across teaching areas and promoting higher-order thinking skills. Less difficulty in ICT integration and literacy and numeracy instruction indicates that teachers can rely on general teaching skills and available resources that are transferable across subjects. Additional insights from respondents provide context to the survey findings. One teacher said that teaching Grade 8 Science for the first time made him question his confidence, especially when handling Biology topics which he himself struggled with when he was a student. However, after attending the orientation on the K–10 curriculum, he found the lessons more manageable, allowing him to relearn key concepts and develop strategies suited to his teaching style. He also noted that teaching an out-of-field subject required extra preparation to minimize errors during actual classroom instruction. These experiences manifest that, while overall instructional challenges are generally low, certain aspects such as applying content knowledge across teaching areas and promoting higher-order thinking still require additional effort from teachers. This reflects a high negative impact on teachers' confidence and workload, particularly when handling out-of-field subjects, highlighting the need for extra preparation and support. The findings indicate that out-of-field teaching does not usually cause major instructional difficulties. Teachers are generally able to handle most content and pedagogy tasks, but some tasks particularly those involving deeper content understanding and higher-order thinking strategies require extra effort. This highlights the importance of providing focused support and training, especially in strengthening content knowledge and teaching strategies for higher-order thinking, to further improve teaching effectiveness in out-of-field subjects.

Du Plessis et al. (2014) emphasized that gaps in content and pedagogical knowledge can make certain aspects of out-of-field teaching more challenging, such as applying content knowledge across areas and using higher-order teaching strategies, highlighting the need for focused professional development and support.

b. Learning Environment

Table 7
The Instructional Challenges Encountered by teachers in Out-of-Field Teaching in Terms of Learning Environment

Learning Environment	Mean	Description
1. I am concerned about my ability to establish safe and secure learning environments to enhance learning through the consistent implementation of policies, guidelines and procedures.	2.85	Agree
2. I am challenged in addressing individual needs effectively and creating a consistently fair learning environment for all students.	2.93	Agree

3. I struggle to manage classroom structure and activities effectively because my limited subject knowledge impacts my ability to plan and implement engaging lessons.	2.33	Disagree
4. My lack of confidence in the subject matter makes it challenging to encourage and support active learner participation.	2.67	Agree
5. I struggle to connect the subject matter to students' real-world experiences and interests due to my limited knowledge.	2.22	Disagree
Mean	2.60	Agree

Table 7 displays the instructional challenges experienced by teachers who are engaged in out-of-field teaching in terms of learning environment. Establishing a safe and secure learning environment, addressing individual needs and creating a fair learning environment, and encouraging active learner participation are challenging to the teachers as shown by their agreement. However, they **disagree** that managing classroom structure and activities and connecting lessons to students' real-world experiences are challenging.

The overall mean of 2.60 interpreted as **Agree** indicates that teachers experience some challenge in managing classroom environments. The results show that teachers face moderate challenges in creating a supportive classroom. These challenges can come from limited knowledge of the subject, which may affect confidence and classroom management. These challenges indicate a high negative impact on teachers' ability to manage classrooms effectively, especially when teaching unfamiliar subjects. In an interview conducted with the teachers, one teacher said that managing the classroom is harder when teaching an out-of-field subject, which can affect confidence and teaching. Another teacher said that teaching Values Education does not affect her confidence much, which means challenges can be different depending on the subject and preparation. Connecting lessons to real-life situations seems easier because teachers can use general teaching skills and creativity. The findings show that out-of-field teaching can moderately affect how teachers manage the classroom. Teachers can usually handle lessons, but some parts like making sure the classroom is fair and helping students participate need more effort. This means teachers can benefit from support and training, especially in managing the classroom and building confidence, to help them teach out-of-field subjects more effectively.

The findings of the present study is supported by the findings of McConney & Price (2009) that out-of-field teaching can moderately affect teachers' ability to manage classroom environments and support student participation, emphasizing the importance of professional development and institutional support.

c. Diversity of Learners

Table 8
The Instructional Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Out-of-Field Teaching in Terms of Diversity of Learners

Diversity of Learners	Mean	Description
1. It is difficult to use differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths and experiences.	2.48	Disagree
2. I find it challenging to establish a learner centered culture by using strategies that respond to their diverse linguistic, cultural, socio-economic, and religious backgrounds of my students.	2.67	Agree
3. My lack of subject-specific knowledge limits my ability to effectively support learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents in this subject area.	2.63	Agree
4. I struggle to provide adequate support for learners in difficult circumstances when teaching this subject, as I may not be aware of the specific challenges they face.	2.48	Disagree
5. I lack the cultural understanding and subject-specific knowledge needed to effectively teach learners from indigenous groups in this subject area.	2.70	Agree
Mean	2.59	Agree

Table 8 shows the instructional challenges faced by teachers in out-of-field teaching in terms of diversity learners. The teachers **agree** that establishing a learner-centered culture that responds to students' diverse linguistic, cultural, socio-economic, and religious backgrounds, supporting learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents, and teaching learners from indigenous groups are challenging. They however, **disagree** that using developmentally appropriate learning experiences, and supporting learners in difficult are challenging.

The overall mean of 2.59 or **Agree** shows that teachers in out-of-field teaching face moderate challenges in meeting the diverse needs of their students, including cultural and linguistic differences, support for learners with special needs, and teaching indigenous learners. These challenges can arise from limited subject knowledge or lack of experience with certain learner groups. This suggests a high negative impact on teachers' capacity to address diverse learner needs effectively without additional support. A teacher-respondent emphasized the importance of preparation and understanding students' needs before teaching. Another teacher shared that self-study and collaboration with colleagues help her address student needs more effectively. These insights support the results of the study that while some aspects are manageable to the teachers, other tasks require extra attention and preparation. The findings indicate that out-of-field

teaching can moderately affect teachers' ability to address learner diversity. This highlights the need for targeted support and professional development, such as training on differentiated instruction and culturally responsive teaching, to help teachers improve effectiveness in out-of-field subjects. This supports the findings of Hobbs & Porsch (2021) that out-of-field teaching can moderately affect teachers' ability to respond to learner diversity, including addressing cultural, linguistic, and special needs, highlighting the importance of targeted professional development and support.

d. Curriculum and Planning

Table 9
The Instructional Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Out-of-Field Teaching in Terms of Curriculum and Planning

Curriculum and Planning	Mean	Description
1. I find it difficult to develop and apply effective teaching strategies that are developmentally sequenced and aligned with curriculum requirements when teaching this subject outside my area of expertise.	2.48	Disagree
2. It is challenging to set achievable yet challenging learning outcomes that are aligned with learning competencies.	2.85	Agree
3. I struggle to effectively collaborate with colleagues to evaluate the design of learning programs for this subject.	2.30	Disagree
4. I struggle in developing and organizing appropriate teaching resources for this subject due to my limited familiarity with the content and relevant resources.	2.59	Agree
5. Adapting curriculum and teaching strategies to meet the diverse learning needs of students in this subject is more challenging.	3.00	Agree
Mean	2.64	Agree

Table 9 shows the instructional challenges faced by teachers in out-of-field teaching, along curriculum and planning.. The teachers **agree** that adapting curriculum and teaching strategies to meet diverse learning needs, setting achievable yet challenging learning outcomes aligned with competencies, and developing and organizing appropriate teaching resources for this subject due to limited familiarity are challenging to them. On the other hand, they disagree that developing teaching strategies aligned with the curriculum, and collaborating with colleagues on program design are challenging.

The overall mean of 2.64% which is interpreted as **Agree** indicates that teachers engaged in out-of-field teaching face moderate challenges in planning and implementing the curriculum, particularly in adapting strategies to students' needs and setting

appropriate learning outcomes. During the interview, one teacher highlighted the importance of attending seminars and seeking mentoring to improve curriculum planning and lesson delivery. Teacher X also mentioned that preparing instructional materials in advance and working closely with colleagues helps in managing curriculum requirements. These shared experiences support the survey results that while some tasks are manageable, others like curriculum adaptation require additional effort. The findings indicate that out-of-field teaching can moderately affect teachers' ability to plan and implement the curriculum effectively. Teachers can handle most planning tasks, but adapting the curriculum, setting suitable learning outcomes, and adjusting strategies to students' diverse needs require extra effort. This highlights a high negative impact on teachers' planning workload and confidence in delivering curriculum outside their specialization. This emphasizes the need for professional support, mentoring, training, and collaboration to improve curriculum planning and lesson delivery in out-of-field subjects. Tran (2023), in his study found that teaching out-of-field subjects can influence teachers' sense of competence and confidence, highlighting that challenges in curriculum adaptation and planning may be related to how teachers perceive and respond to unfamiliar subject demands.

e. Assessment and Reporting

Table 10
The Instructional Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Out-of-Field Teaching in Terms of Assessment and Reporting

Assessment and Reporting	Mean	Description
1. I lack confidence designing and selecting appropriate assessment strategies that accurately measure student understanding.	2.41	Disagree
2. I struggle to effectively monitor and evaluate learner progress and achievement.	2.00	Disagree
3. I find it challenging to provide effective feedback to improve learning.	2.37	Disagree
4. My lack of confidence in my subject matter expertise makes it difficult to clearly communicate learner needs, progress, and achievement to parents and other stakeholders.	2.11	Disagree
5. I find it challenging to use assessment data to enhance my teaching practices and programs.	2.44	Disagree
Mean	2.27	Disagree

Table 10 shows the challenges faced by teachers in out-of-field teaching, in terms of assessment and reporting. The data reveals that assessment and reporting is not a challenge to the teachers teaching out-of-field subjects. This can be attributed to the regular Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions they have where they receive guidance, share best practices, and gain professional support from colleagues in terms of plan

assessments, providing feedback, and using assessment results to improve teaching. The support from LAC sessions and collaborative practices enables them to handle assessment tasks more confidently. Teacher Z mentioned that to ensure that assessments are accurate and effective, relies on self-study and asks help from colleagues.

Abella et al., (2021), who examined assessment in out-of-field teaching. identified potential challenges in assessment while this study found that teachers are generally not challenged by assessment and reporting regardless whether they teach their major subjects or subjects outside their field of expertise.

f. Summary of the Instructional Challenges

Table 11
Summary of the Instructional Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Out-of-Field Teaching

Instructional Challenges	Overall Mean	Description
Content and Pedagogy	2.47	Disagree
Learning Environment	2.60	Agree
Diversity of Learners	2.59	Agree
Curriculum and Planning	2.64	Agree
Assessment and Reporting	2.27	Disagree

Table 11 presents the summary of the instructional challenges encountered by teachers engaged in out-of-field teaching across five key dimensions. Among these dimensions, Curriculum and Planning obtained the highest overall mean of 2.64 indicating that it is the most challenging area for teachers. This suggests that teachers experience greater difficulty in adapting the curriculum, setting appropriate learning outcomes, and preparing teaching resources when teaching teach out-of-field subjects. Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners are also challenging for teachers. These indicate that limited subject familiarity may affect teachers' confidence in managing classrooms, addressing individual learner needs, and responding to cultural, linguistic, and learning differences among students.

On the other hand, Content and Pedagogy and Assessment and Reporting were perceived as less challenging. This suggests that teachers are generally able to manage content delivery, teaching strategies, and assessment practices by relying on transferable pedagogical skills, prior teaching experience, and collaborative support such as Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions.

Overall, the findings indicate that while out-of-field teaching does not result in severe instructional difficulties, it poses moderate challenges particularly in curriculum planning, classroom management, and addressing learner diversity. These areas require additional preparation, confidence-building, and institutional support. The results highlight the importance of targeted professional development, mentoring, and collaborative practices to strengthen teachers' capacity to effectively teach out-of-field subjects.

3. Is there a significant difference on the instructional challenges encountered by the teachers when grouped according to profile?

Table 12
Result of the Test of Significant Difference on the Instructional Challenges Encountered by the Respondents When Grouped According to Profile

Profile	Significance F	Decision	Remarks
Highest Educational Attainment	.370	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Major/Field of Specialization	.204	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Subject Currently Taught	.291	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Number of Years Out-of-Field Teaching	.539	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Number of trainings related to the subject taught attended in the last 3 years	.722	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 12 reveals the result of the test of significant difference in the instructional challenges encountered by the respondents when grouped according to profile using Analysis of Variance F - test at .05 level of significance.

As shown in the table, the significance F-values for all the profile variables are greater than .05 which resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference in the instructional challenges encountered by the respondents when grouped according to highest educational attainment, major/field of specialization, subject currently taught, number of years out-of-field teaching and number of trainings related to the subject taught attended in the last 3 years.

4. What coping strategies do teachers use when teaching out-of-field subjects?

Table 13
Coping Strategies Employed by Teachers When Teaching Out-of-Field Subjects

Coping Strategies	Mean	Description
1. I seek professional development opportunities to improve my competence in out-of-field teaching.	3.30	Frequent
2. I attend seminars, workshops, or training sessions to enhance my teaching skills in unfamiliar subjects.	2.48	Sometimes
3. I collaborate with colleagues to enhance my teaching strategies in unfamiliar subjects.	3.37	Always
4. I actively look for instructional materials to aid my teaching in an unfamiliar subject.	3.44	Always
5. I adjust my teaching strategies to effectively deliver lessons in an unfamiliar subject.	3.48	Always
6. I seek mentorship or guidance from experienced teachers when handling out-of-field subjects.	3.26	Always
7. I engage in self-directed learning to improve my understanding of an unfamiliar subject.	3.52	Always
8. I use technology and online resources to enhance my knowledge and teaching strategies.	3.48	Always
9. I establish clear learning goals to help guide my instruction in an unfamiliar subject.	3.59	Always

Table 13 reveals the coping strategies teachers use when handling out-of-field subjects. The overall mean of 3.34 interpreted as **Always** indicates that teachers regularly use various strategies to manage challenges in teaching out-of-field subjects. Engaging in self-directed learning to improve understanding of an unfamiliar subject, adjusting teaching strategies to effectively deliver lessons in an unfamiliar subject, using technology and online resources to enhance knowledge and teaching strategies, actively looking for instructional materials to aid teaching in an unfamiliar subject, collaborating with colleagues to enhance teaching strategies in unfamiliar subjects, and seeking mentorship or guidance from experienced teachers when handling out-of-field subjects are **always** resorted to by teachers.

Teachers **frequently** seek professional development opportunities to improve their competence in out-of-field teaching and **sometimes** attend seminars, workshops, or training sessions to enhance my teaching skills in unfamiliar subjects.

The results show that teachers actively use a variety of coping strategies to handle the challenges of teaching out-of-field subject. Teacher A shared that attending seminars and seeking mentorship are effective strategies, while another teacher emphasized that he employs self-study and collaborates with colleagues. Another teacher reported attending training sessions and watching free online lectures to strengthen areas that needed improvement, and creating easy-to-read notes to explain lessons more clearly.

These sharing support the survey results and show that teachers rely on self-directed learning, preparation, and peer support as key coping mechanisms. The findings indicate that teachers proactively use coping strategies to improve their skills and teaching effectiveness in out-of-field subjects. Regular use of strategies like goal-setting, self-study, collaboration, professional development, mentorship, and technology use helps maintain competence and motivation despite the challenges. This supports the findings of Arendain & Limpot (2021), which highlight the importance of peer collaboration, professional development, self-directed learning, intrinsic motivation, and access to resources in overcoming instructional challenges in out-of-field teaching. Overall, coping strategies serve as key tools for teachers to remain effective and confident even when teaching out-of-field subjects.

5. Is there a significant difference in the coping strategies employed by teachers when grouped according to their profile?

Table 14
Result of the Test of Significant Difference in the Coping Strategies Employed by the Respondents when Grouped According to Profile

Profile	Significance F	Decision	Remarks
Highest Educational Attainment	.817	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Major/Feld of Specialization	.966	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Subject Currently Taught	.365	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Number of Years Out-of-Field Teaching	.742	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Number of trainings related to the subject taught attended in the last 3 years (5-6)	.021	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 14 reveals the result of the test of significant difference in the coping strategies employed by the respondents when grouped according to profile using Analysis of Variance F - test at .05 level of significance.

As shown in the table, the significance F-values for the profile highest educational attainment, major/field of specialization and subject currently taught, are greater than .05 which resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

The significance F-value for the number of trainings related to the subject taught attended in the last 3 years is less than .05 significance level resulting to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that there is a significant difference in the coping strategies employed by the respondents when grouped according to the number of trainings related to the subject taught attended in the last 3 years.

The results indicates that the coping strategies applied by the respondents are not affected by their demographic profile except for the training they have attended. The findings show that teachers who attended more trainings tend to employ a wider variety of coping strategies when handling out-of-field subjects.

6. What is the impact of out-of-field teaching on their instructional competence and motivation?

a. Impact on Competence

Table 15
Impact of Out-of-Field Teaching on Teachers' Instructional Competence

Impact on Competence	Mean	Description
1. Teaching outside my expertise has affected my confidence in delivering lessons effectively.	2.41	Low
2. My instructional strategies are less effective when teaching subjects outside my specialization.	2.63	High
3. I feel competent in handling out-of-field subjects after gaining teaching experience.	2.93	High
4. Teaching a subject outside my specialization makes lesson planning more challenging for me.	3.07	High
5. I feel more pressured when assessing student performance in a subject outside my expertise.	2.70	High
6. My ability to manage the classroom is affected when teaching an unfamiliar subject.	2.67	High
7. Teaching out-of-field subjects requires me to spend more time preparing lessons.	3.30	Very High
8. I find it harder to answer students' questions confidently in a subject outside my expertise.	2.67	High
9. I struggle to integrate real-life examples when teaching subjects outside my specialization.	2.48	Low
10. Teaching outside my specialization limits my ability to use diverse teaching strategies.	2.56	High
In their instructional strategies.Mean	2.74	High

Table 15 shows the impact of teaching out-of-field subjects on teachers' instructional competence. The overall mean of 2.74 indicates that teaching-out-of-field has high impact on the teachers' competence. Specifically, this has a **very high impact**

on their preparation of lessons. Teaching out-of-field makes lesson planning more challenging for the teachers in lesson planning and makes them less effective in their instructional strategies. Teachers are less effective when teaching subjects outside my specialization. Teachers handling out-of-field subjects feel more pressured in assessing students' performance. Furthermore, teaching outside their specialization limits their ability to use diverse teaching strategies and find it harder to answer students' questions confidently.

The results suggest that teaching out-of-field subjects has a high negative impact on teachers' instructional competence, because it often requires extra lesson preparation, careful planning, classroom management, adapting instructional strategies, handling student questions confidently, and applying diverse teaching methods. Most tasks demand additional effort and adjustment, which leads to a higher reported impact on competence. Some teachers, however, feel more competent after gaining experience which implies that practice and exposure can improve their self-efficacy over time. Teacher A shared that teaching out-of-field initially reduces her confidence but motivates improvement and flexibility. Teacher Y reported mixed effects on motivation: a short break from their main subject increases motivation, but preparing instructional materials on weekends can be tiring. Teacher K noted that teaching subjects like Chemistry and Physics encouraged him to use his own learning experiences to guide lesson delivery, which gradually improved his competence. The results of the study show that while teachers face challenges, continued exposure and adaptation help enhance competence. While confidence and effectiveness may initially be affected, practice, adaptation, and experience can improve competence over time. This supports the findings of Edulan, and Fajardo (2024) Abella et al. (2021) that out-of-field teaching poses challenges in lesson preparation, classroom management, and confidence, confirming that institutional support and professional development are crucial in helping teachers overcome these difficulties.

b. Impact on Motivation

Table 16
Impact of Out-of-Field Teaching on Teachers' Motivation

Impact on Motivation	Mean	Description
1. Teaching outside my field has motivated me to improve my knowledge and teaching strategies.	3.44	Very High
2. Teaching out-of-field subjects has decreased my enthusiasm and motivation in teaching.	2.59	High
3. Teaching outside my field has pushed me to seek more guidance and support from colleagues.	3.30	High
4. Despite the challenges, I believe teaching out-of-field subjects has contributed to my professional growth.	3.41	Very High
5. I feel frustrated when I am assigned to teach subjects outside my specialization.	2.48	Low

6. Teaching outside my expertise makes me feel less satisfied with my job.	2.41	Low
7. I feel a sense of accomplishment when I successfully teach a subject outside my field.	3.48	Very High
8. Being assigned to teach out-of-field subjects makes me feel less confident about my career growth.	2.04	Low
9. I am more motivated to attend professional development programs to improve my teaching skills.	3.48	Very High
10. Teaching outside my specialization has made me more open to learning new concepts and skills.	3.52	Very High
Mean	3.01	High

Table 16 presents the impact of teaching out-of-field subjects on teachers' instructional motivation.. Teaching outside their specialization has made the teacher more open to learning new concepts and skills, motivated them to improve their knowledge and teaching strategies and motivated them more to attend professional development programs to improve their teaching skills. Teaching out-of-field has highly impacted the teachers in terms of decreased enthusiasm and motivation in teaching and in seeking support and guidance from colleagues. .

The results suggest that teaching out-of-field subjects can both be a challenge and motivation for teachers. While some tasks may temporarily reduce enthusiasm or job satisfaction, teachers often respond by seeking support, engaging in professional development, and improving their teaching strategies. One teacher shared that the Department of Education provided technical assistance throughout the school year, which helped him manage the demands of out-of-field teaching. He emphasized that resiliency and personal determination are important for coping with challenges and maintaining motivation. These findings indicate that teaching out-of-field subjects can foster professional growth and enhance motivation. External support, mentorship, intrinsic motivation, and access to resources help teachers navigate unfamiliar subjects effectively. This supports the findings of Tran (2023) which highlight that out-of-field teaching can develop adaptability, resilience, and professional competencies. Edulan and Fajardo (2024) also emphasized that intrinsic motivation, mentorship, and resource access are crucial in sustaining teacher motivation, reinforcing the importance of support systems for teachers handling out-of-field subjects.

7. Is there a significant relationship between coping strategies and impact of out-of-field teaching?

Table 17
Result of the Test of Significant Relationship Between Coping Strategies and the Impact of Out-of-field Teaching

Group	Significance F	Decision	Remarks
Coping Strategies And Impact of Out-of-field Teaching	.239	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 17 shows the result of the test of significant relationship between the coping strategies and the impact of out-of-field teaching using Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation r-test at .05 level of significance.

As shown in the table, the significance r -value between the coping strategies and impact of out-of-field teaching is greater than .05 significance level which resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Hence, there is no significant relationship between the coping strategies and impact of out-of-field teaching of the respondents. This is because, although coping strategies help teachers manage challenges, they mainly enhance their motivation and confidence rather than directly reducing the overall impact of teaching out-of-field. Despite frequent use of coping strategies such as self-study, mentorship, and collaboration, these do not completely eliminate the impact on confidence or lesson delivery. This aligns with the quantitative result of no significant correlation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions can be drawn: Teaching out-of-field has corresponding challenges to teachers in various instructional domains, including content and pedagogy, classroom management, addressing learner diversity, curriculum planning, and assessment. To cope with these challenges, teachers employ several strategies such as establishing clear learning goals, seeking support from colleagues, engaging in self-directed learning, and adjusting their teaching approaches to better deliver lessons.

Teaching out-of-field subjects highly impacts teachers' instructional competence and motivation. This includes increased pressure in lesson planning, classroom management, and responding to student questions, while also promoting professional growth, openness to new learning, and a sense of accomplishment.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

The Curriculum Implementation Division, should design relevant training programs and provide technical assistance to address the specific needs of teachers teaching out-of-field particularly on curriculum adaptation, lesson planning, and application of content and pedagogical strategies.

The Human Resource Management Office, should use the findings as basis in teacher recruitment considering teachers with appropriate specialization.

Given the high negative impact of out-of-field teaching on teachers' competence, school administrators should prioritize targeted training, mentoring, and provision of teaching resources to help teachers handle out-of-field subjects more effectively and confidently.

Based on the findings showing that out-of-field teaching has a high negative impact on teachers' instructional competence, highly proficient teachers must provide mentoring and coaching support to out-of-field teachers to help improve their competence and instructional effectiveness. This includes guidance in lesson planning, classroom management, and adapting curriculum to diverse learners.

Proficient Teachers must apply effective coping strategies identified in the study, such as self-directed learning, collaboration with colleagues, use of online resources, and reflective practices, to enhance teaching practices and deliver lessons more confidently.

For the Researcher to utilize insights from the study to deepen understanding of out-of-field teaching challenges and contribute to personal growth in educational research.

Future Researchers may use this study as a reference to explore further issues on out-of-field teaching, teacher competence, motivation, coping strategies, and targeted interventions for high-challenge areas identified in the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical principles in educational research. Prior to data gathering, permission to conduct the study was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent and the School Head of Isabela School of Arts and Trades (ISAT)-Main. The respondents were properly informed about the nature and purpose of the study, and their participation was strictly voluntary. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before the administration of the survey questionnaire and the conduct of interviews. Confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were ensured throughout the research process, and all information gathered was used solely for academic purposes. Participants were also informed of their right to decline or withdraw

from the study at any point without penalty. The researcher observed honesty, objectivity, and integrity in the collection, analysis, interpretation, and presentation of data.

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